

Correction to: Comorbidities in Dravet Syndrome and Lennox–Gastaut Syndrome

Francesca Marchese¹ · Simona Cappelletti² · Melissa Filippini³ · Cristiana Alessia Guido^{4,5} · Claudia Passamonti⁶ · Barbara Pucci⁷ · Michela Sole¹ · Pasquale Striano^{1,8,9}

© The Author(s) 2021

Correction to: *SN Comprehensive Clinical Medicine* (2021) 3:2167–2179
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s42399-021-00989-y>

The article Comorbidities in Dravet Syndrome and Lennox–Gastaut Syndrome, written by Francesca Marchese, Simona Cappelletti, Melissa Filippini, Cristiana Alessia Guido, Claudia Passamonti, Barbara Pucci, Michela Sole and Pasquale Striano, was originally published Online First without Open Access. After publication in volume 3, issue 10, pages 2167–2179, the author decided to opt for Open Choice and to make the article an Open Access publication. Therefore, the copyright of the article has been changed to © The Author(s) 2021 and the article is forthwith distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution.

Open Access This article is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License, which permits use, sharing, adaptation, distribution and reproduction in any medium or format, as long as you give appropriate credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons licence, and indicate if changes were made. The images or other third party material in this article are included in the article's Creative Commons licence, unless indicated otherwise in a credit line to the material. If material is not included in the article's Creative Commons licence and your intended use is not permitted by statutory regulation or exceeds the permitted use, you will need to obtain permission directly from the copyright holder. To view a copy of this licence, visit <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.

Publisher's Note Springer Nature remains neutral with regard to jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations.

The original article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42399-021-00989-y>.

✉ Pasquale Striano
strianop@gmail.com; pasqualestriano@gaslini.org

¹ IRCCS “G. Gaslini” Children’s Hospital, Genoa, Italy

² Ospedale Pediatrico Bambino Gesù, Rome, Italy

³ IRCCSBellaria Hospital, Bologna, Italy

⁴ Department of Maternal Sciences, Pediatric Neurology Division, Sapienza University, Rome, Italy

⁵ Department of Developmental and Social Psychology, Faculty of Medicine and Psychology, Sapienza University of Rome, Rome, Italy

⁶ Riuniti Hospital, Ancona, Italy

⁷ University of Siena, Siena, Italy

⁸ Department of Neurosciences, Genetics, Maternal and Child Health, University of Genova, RehabilitationGenova, Ophthalmology, Italy

⁹ Pediatric Neurology and Muscular Diseases Unit, IRCCS Istituto “G. Gaslini”, Via Gaslini 5, 16147 Genova, Italy